

AN INTEGRATED DIAGNOSTIC SUPPORT SYSTEM APPROACH
TO FAULT ISOLATION IN THE OPERATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

James L. Cigler

Test And Monitoring Systems Office
Naval Sea Systems Command
Washington, DC 20362-5101
(202) 692-0170

ABSTRACT

The Navy Integrated Diagnostic Support System (IDSS) program is developing software tools required for a systems engineering approach to providing an improved fault isolation capability for the operational level maintenance technician. The success of the diagnostic process depends on the integration of design for testability, development of test procedures based on the optimum design, authoring of the execution software and analysis of results of diagnostic sessions as feedback to the system expert knowledge data base.

The IDSS software tools are described and the status of the IDSS Research and Development effort is presented.

INTRODUCTION

The success of a diagnostic process in maintaining complex systems depends upon several elements such as status monitoring, built-in test, error logging, maintenance aids and automatic and manual test equipment. Effective technical manuals and technician training are also required to support this testing. The Navy Integrated Diagnostic Support System (IDSS) is a research and development program which is developing a new "integrated" approach to diagnostics with a major emphasis on software tools.

BACKGROUND

Up until about thirty years ago, the ability to diagnose Naval weapon system problems depended solely upon the intelligence and skill of human beings. A little training, a few schematics, some general purpose test instruments and, preferably, some experience was all that was needed to fix any problem.

As systems became more complex, Automatic Test Equipment (ATE) which could automatically sequence through instrument stimuli/responses under

control of software became important. As systems became even more complex and ATE and its software became more complex and expensive, the Design for Testability discipline tried to shift some of the testing burden back on the prime system designers. As technology made circuitry smaller and lighter, Built-in Test (BIT) became more cost-effective. For several years, BIT caused more problems than it solved with its high false alarm rates, but now that problem is better under control.

Now we have come full circle. There is a realization that having a person in the loop to control the diagnostic process is the best way after all, but he is going to need significant help from computer-based tools to handle the complexity of modern systems.

DEFINITION OF INTEGRATED DIAGNOSTICS

Integrated Diagnostics is defined as "a structured process which maximizes the effectiveness of diagnostics by integrating the individual diagnostic elements of testability, automatic testing, manual testing, training, maintenance aiding and technical information". Integrated diagnostics is accomplished by using a well-planned combination of automatic and manual test procedures.

In addition to integrating across diagnostic elements, Integrated Diagnostics provides for integration across maintenance levels. This is in direct response to the number one problem in avionics testing, the Retest OKay (RTOK) or Can Not Duplicate (CND) where a fault is indicated at one level of maintenance (field test) and not indicated at the next level (shop test).

A third area of integration for Integrated Diagnostics is across system development and support phases. All too often, engineering data used to design and build a system is not transferred to or used by personnel responsible for developing the system's diagnostic capability. Integrated Diagnostics

attempts to reduce the great amount of reverse engineering that goes on in developing test programs, training, and technical manuals.

IDSS TOOL SET AND DATA FLOW

The IDSS is being developed by the Naval Sea Systems Command with Harris Corporation, Government Support Systems Division, as the prime contractor. The IDSS program is structured to support hardware design through its testability analyzer tool and diagnostic software design through its diagnostic authoring tool. Design data is processed by the Weapon System Testability Analyzer (WSTA) tool. Authoring of the diagnostic knowledge data base requires use of the Adaptive Diagnostic Authoring (ADA) and Technical Information And Training Authoring (TIATA) tools. Field application of the diagnostic knowledge data base for fault isolation sessions is via the Adaptive Diagnostic Subsystem (ADS) "shell", and the process of evaluation of maintenance data via the Feedback Analyzer (FA) aids in providing life-cycle support of the fielded system.

WEAPON SYSTEM TESTABILITY ANALYZER TOOL

The Weapon System Testability Analyzer (WSTA) tool inputs detailed hardware topology and logistic data and creates a dependency model which is used to generate a test strategy that is very near the optimal, in terms of minimizing average test times or test costs, and provides testability data and recommendations to the design engineer.

CAE input ... The engineering data required by IDSS is a description of the topology of the system. The data may be transferred directly from a Computer-aided Engineering (CAE) workstation or, more likely, would require a language translator. The data representation format chosen by the IDSS program for CAE data is the VHSIC Hardware Description Language (VHDL), IEEE Standard 1076 (1). The VHDL contains entities which describe a hardware unit's interface to the external world and "bodies" which describe the internal workings of the hardware. Each entity may have multiple bodies (e.g., a behavioral description and a structural description).

Since the WSTA utilizes only structural descriptions, an IDSS subset of VHDL has been defined (IVHDL). The IVHDL subset includes only "concurrent" VHDL syntax. The IDSS CAE preprocessor reads the IEEE-1076 VHDL descriptions, parses out non-IVHDL code, flattens the hierarchy and enables WSTA to generate

the appropriate dependency model. The IVHDL is used extensively to describe digital, analog and hybrid circuits.

A dependency model may be informally thought of as being composed of components and test points. This makes it comparable to the netlist associated with a hardware description, such as VHDL. The model is more properly thought of as being composed of aspects and events (tests). Also, a physical component may be represented in the model as having several aspects of failure. A dependency model establishes that certain events depend upon certain aspects which, in turn, depend on other events.

The IDSS CAE preprocessor, actually the "front end" of the WSTA tool is expected to automate well over ninety percent of the model preparation task and is a significant step toward user acceptance of dependency modelling.

Logistic data input ... The logistic data required is primarily a compilation of component failure rates, test times and test resources. These are used by the WSTA to compute the optimal diagnostic strategy. The data representation format chosen by the IDSS program for logistic data is the Logistic Support Analysis Record (LSAR), in the MIL-STD-1388 format used by all the Services. Usually, when a system is under development, its logistic data consists only of predicted values or is incomplete. The WSTA is able to allocate reasonable default values or allow interactive user assignments.

User input ... The dependency model of a system or subsystem may be entered directly into the WSTA by using its Model Editor. This is definitely required when the system is non-electronic (e.g., mechanical, hydraulic) and would not have a CAE data base. The Editor is also needed to work around a small number of topology features from a CAE data base which are not automatically translatable to the dependency model structure.

Test strategy ... The WSTA uses the system dependency model to generate a test strategy (or fault tree). This tree is optimized with respect to criteria specified by the user. The most common criteria would be to generate a test strategy which minimizes the mean time to isolate (MTTI) system faults. Cost to isolate could also be used as a basis for optimization.

Design feedback ... The WSTA calculates static (topological) testability figures of merit such as average inherent ambiguity group size and feedback loop characteristics, plus dynamic (test-strategy-based) figures of merit such as mean or maximum time to fault

isolate. It also provides guidance to the designer on the optimal placement of test points (for BIT, ATE, manual probing) based upon the fault isolation data each test point can provide. Finally, it gives recommendations on the best place to break feedback loops to decrease ambiguity group sizes.

ADAPTIVE DIAGNOSTIC AUTHORIZING TOOL

A test procedure in IDSS is a self-contained object which may be invoked by automatic test (BIT) or the technician (such as a request for an observation or measurement). The procedures may be loaded into the system memory as augmented BIT software (e.g., patterns for driving boundary scan latches) or into a standalone troubleshooting aid as external test software. Thus, the test procedure might be coded in Ada, microcode, ATLAS, etc., or might be pure data. The actual mechanism for generating and validating the test procedures is done outside of the IDSS tool set.

The IDSS Adaptive Diagnostic Authoring (ADA) tool inputs the test procedure in response to the WSTA generated strategy. In addition, production rules may also be entered by the test engineer. These rules are generally independent of the dependency model relationships. For example, a rule might be "if a given component is hot, suspect a failure in a second component.

Technical information and training data are also inducted into the ADA via the IDSS Technical Information And Training Authoring (TIATA) tool to provide consistent and coordinated diagnostic assistance to the field technician. Digitized mechanical drawings, schematics and parts lists are entered into the diagnostic knowledge data base and associated with particular events in the diagnostic strategy. All data are in the Initial Graphics Exchange Standard (IGES) format per the DoD Computer-assisted Acquisition and Logistics Support (CALS) requirements for paperless exchange of technical information. Digitized training data (e.g., training on the use of a type of test equipment) are also associated with the diagnostic strategy. Multiple levels of training material may be entered via the ADA tool to satisfy the needs of both the novice and experienced technician.

All of the diagnostic data and supporting data are stored on a central Common Diagnostic Data Base (CDDB), one per system type. As this data is required to support systems at particular field sites, the CDDB data is copied, along

with any site-specific data, onto Weapon-specific Data Base (WDB) tapes.

ADAPTIVE DIAGNOSTIC SUBSYSTEM

As part of the IDSS program, an intelligent troubleshooting aid will be located at the site of each system being tested, and is called the Adaptive Diagnostic Subsystem (ADS). The ADS in its production configuration may be either a stand-alone device, a device which is loosely coupled to the system via a standard interface buss, or a completely embedded device. In any case, the ADS software is strictly generic, with all system-specific information found in its WDB.

The ADS contains logic to utilize the diagnostic resource (BIT, augmented BIT, guided manual troubleshooting, technician inputs, sequential replacement) which will have the most likelihood of success based upon the diagnostic session results up to that point. The ADS design philosophy is to keep the technician in control of the diagnostic process and provide insight to him. ADS provides the technician with a recommended next best test or a recommended repair action. It also provides a running estimate of how much longer the diagnostic process will take so that the technician may elect to take a less economical repair action if the situation demands a quick turnaround of the system.

ADS knowledge update ... Maintenance data resulting from successful completion of a diagnostic session/repair action is fed back from the ADS to enable "learning". The ADS at each site updates its initial WDB (becoming a local Diagnostic Data Base, LDDB) at a relatively high rate. In addition, the data from each LDDB is periodically transferred back to a central location via the Feedback Analyzer (FA) for further processing.

The ADS remembers its successes and failures and automatically "adapts" its strategy. It watches for any components whose failure rates are sharply different from the modelled rates. It also remembers the environment for each diagnostic session. For example, a component may experience the same intermittent failure every time an antenna is turned on. In addition, the ADS can be told that a particular test instrument is not available, and adjust its strategy thereafter to work around that test. After ADS directs a successful field repair, it prepares a data package to accompany the replaced unit on its way to the shop, or next level of repair.

This provides some insight into the original system-level problem.

FEEDBACK ANALYZER

The IDSS Feedback Analyzer (FA) tool collects data from each of the ADS sites and performs a statistical analysis of the data to determine if a site's experience is globally valid or just valid for that particular site (because of environment, system configuration, maintenance policy, technician training, etc.). For the latter case, the learned data is tagged as site-peculiar. For the former case, the data on the CDDB (failure rates, test times, etc.) are updated. Data is also collected from the maintenance shops which indicate if suspect cards were really faulty or just good cards in an ambiguity group. Finally, if a technician in the field had entered a suggestion which is generally useful, that suggestion is re-entered as a production rule by the test engineer using the ADA tool.

The feedback data, in addition to being used to improve diagnostic procedures and strategy, may also be used to justify engineering changes to the system hardware to improve its testability.

CHARACTERISTICS OF IDSS TOOLS

WSTA. Several testability analysis programs have been developed for digital logic which attempt to measure the difficulty of controlling and observing internal nodes but all have experienced problems (2) including very weak correlation to actual fault isolation difficulty. A more accurate analysis may be achieved using the WSTA dependency model approach which makes use of test strategy information as well as circuit topology information. Other tools using dependency modelling besides WSTA include the Logic Model (LOGMOD) program (3) and the System Testability and Maintenance Program (STAMP) (4). All are applicable to digital, analog and non-electronic systems and all generate a test strategy, or fault isolation tree, which may be used to define the actual diagnostic process.

WSTA Model Generator ... The CAE and LSA data are preprocessed and placed in the data base. Any user data is input through the model editor and validated before being placed in the data base. There are three sets of inputs to the WSTA tool from which the test, testability indicators and testability design recommendations are derived; these are 1) test dependencies, 2) test

characteristics, and 3) failure characteristics. The WSTA takes the inputs and develops a dependency table which defines the first order dependency model (based on a single fault assumption).

Static testability indicators ... The WSTA calculates static testability indicators based only upon the topology of the system dependencies. Static indicators include: Inherent fault isolation levels, Component involvement ratios, ambiguity group composition, size, distribution, feedback loop composition, and aggregate failure rate.

Test strategy generator ... The WSTA uses the Time Efficient Sequencer of Tests (TEST) algorithm (5) which employs top-down search algorithms that integrate concepts from the information theory approach. AI techniques are used to subdue the computational explosion of the optimal test sequencing problem. An approximate cost-to-go is derived from information-theoretic concepts of Huffman coding and entropy. Using these bounds, TEST enables optimal solutions which are intractable for other techniques.

The search for an optimal test tree is, in general, an NP-complete problem (although special cases can be solved in polynomial time) and an algorithm cannot guarantee a solution without an inordinately large amount of partial-tree solutions. The TEST algorithm is a significant advance over previous test tree optimization algorithms, in that it applies both top-down and bottom-up search techniques to limit the combinational explosion of possible partial-solution trees that are to be explored.

The WSTA tool provides two options that permit a tradeoff between optimality and execution time. Option 1 is a "greedy" test selection process in which, at each node in the current solution tree, the next best test is selected according to some criterion. Option 2 is an e-optimal algorithm that guarantees that the solution tree has a global cost function no greater than $(1+e)$ times that of the optimal tree.

Dynamic testability indicators ... after the WSTA has created the dependency model and generated the optimal test tree, it calculates dynamic testability indicators which are based upon the system topology and the actual sequencing used to test the system. The dynamic testability indicators include: Min/mean max time to isolate, min/mean/max cost to isolate, min/mean/max time to repair, min/mean/max cost to repair, and test/repair tradeoff data.

With the inclusion of logistics data

such as component failure rates and test times in the system model, the dynamic testability indicators reflect the actual operational environment under which the system is to be tested.

Because the TEST algorithm creates optimal or near-optimal test trees, the testability indicators that are based on this tree reflect only information about tests and design structure and not any peculiarity of the algorithm. To be consistent with the TEST assumptions, the indicator calculations are also conditioned on a single fault-state assumption.

Testability advisor ... The static and dynamic testability indicators are presented to the user as textual and graphical reports to provide insight into any problem areas in the system design. In addition, the WSTA provides test point recommendations in the form of a prioritized list of the "diagnostic value" of placing a test point at each node. The most valuable nodes might be candidates for automatic monitoring (BIT) and the block of next most valuable nodes might be connected to interface pins for access by automatic test equipment (ATE). The block of nodes considered least valuable can be considered for deletion. WSTA also provides feedback loop breaking recommendations to the user. It identifies the optimum point to break a loop as well as a list of alternative break points. Testability advisor recommendations can be incorporated by the design engineer and the modified model can be again evaluated by WSTA to determine testability improvements achieved.

The WSTA software has been accepted by Naval Sea Systems Command, and is presently completing Beta site testing. The tool is being applied in testability analysis/BIT assessment on selected components of the V-22 avionics suite. It has also been used to model the MK78 MOD1 Harpoon Missile Simulator in conjunction with the design agents at Naval Ordnance Station, Indian Head Maryland. The software will be released without charge to interested government and industry design facilities in June 1989. All IDSS software will be similarly available upon completion of the tools.

Adaptive Diagnostic Subsystem Tool

The IDSS Adaptive Diagnostic Subsystem (ADS) consists of two major programs: Diagnostic Assistance recommends the next maintenance action and Local Diagnostic Data Base (LDDB) Update is responsible for updating the local diagnostic data base.

Diagnostic Assistance ... The Diagnostic Assistance subprogram reads several kinds of data from the LDDB (test trees, original dependency data, production rules) depending upon the reasoner being used.

With test trees, the troubleshooting procedure to be followed is optimized according to some criteria such as minimizing test time or test costs. The problem with following a fixed test tree sequence (such as a fault tree in a technical manual) is that many assumptions have gone into the sequence. What happens if, during system test, the supervisor won't allow the entering of a certain maintenance mode to run a needed BIT routine or the manual test equipment called for by the next test is not available? Under integrated diagnostics, the test strategy should always allow for alternate or backup diagnostic elements and data to be applied to the problem. The two major alternate approaches, dependency models and production rules are used by ADS.

Test results may come from a variety of sources under integrated diagnostics including system BIT data, portable tester probe data and, very importantly, technician observations. The ADS responds with a recommended maintenance action, either to run a certain test or to remove and replace certain items.

LDDB update ... On a per-session basis, the ADS will update its local diagnostic data base. Logistics parameters such as item failure rates and test times are updated based upon the experience gained from the diagnostic session. The test tree should also be updated if time permits. A sensitivity analysis is made by ADS to determine if the parameters have changed enough to justify recomputing the tree (using the same algorithm as in WSTA). The configuration control of the LDDB is of utmost importance and will vary according to the using activity.

Maintenance aids ... A maintenance aid is an electronic device for communicating maintenance information to a technician. It might be used in a stand-alone mode, perhaps displaying technical information or directing a troubleshooting session or may even serve as a "plug-in" suitcase tester with one or more universal probes. IDSS is evaluating on-going DoD and commercial efforts in this area in an attempt to incorporate technology developments into a suitable unit capable of hosting the ADS software for the purpose of demonstrating the completed IDSS tool set on a unit under test (UUT) in its operational environment.

Maintenance Data ... The ADS tries to

provide the technician with all the information he needs to deal with his current maintenance problem without immersing him in a sea of nonrelevant information. This is essentially a concept of "just in time" embedded training. The ADS can, either automatically or through a user HELP feature, request that technical information of a training segment be pulled from the LDDDB and displayed. If the integrated diagnostics concept is to work, the technician must be given insight into the workings (and failings) of his system and insight into the diagnostic process - but only within the context of the maintenance task at hand.

ADS DESIGN ISSUES (6)

Diagnostic data acquisition ... Intelligent troubleshooting systems can be extremely expensive to build. While the high cost of generating test programs is well documented, there is also an extremely high cost associated with efforts utilizing knowledge engineering or artificial intelligence approaches. Knowledge engineering projects typically require long interviews lasting from months to years with system experts. As the system is upgraded or experiences changes in failure characteristics with age, the requirement for follow-on interviews becomes necessary.

The ADS system-specific information is obtained largely from design databases generated from engineering data during the system design phase and, to a much lesser extent, from knowledge engineering interviews.

Levels Of Intelligence ... A second difficulty with intelligent troubleshooting aids involves a sufficiency/computational tradeoff. As an aid is made more and more capable of handling a large number of faults, its computational demands may become unreasonable for many common diagnostic tasks. This issue is further exacerbated by the possibility that rare, difficult-to-handle faults may cause a disproportionate share of the downtime.

The ADS contains "levels of intelligence". Predictable, well understood faults are isolated using techniques which are pre-computed and require no real online intelligence. Only as these techniques fail are more complex techniques brought into use. These "deeper" strategies contain more complex system models and involve the use of dynamic, real time inferencing, but they are only called if there is some evidence that they are needed.

The system models used by the ADS

borrow liberally from existing technology. The ADS utilizes the optimized pre-computed test tree, the dependency model, a model of component responsibilities (7), and a model of cause-and-effect relationships (8). Responsibility modelling involves identifying certain types of components as being responsible for supporting certain types of tests. For example, the type "diode" may be assigned responsibility for maintaining the peak voltage of a waveform. Finally, local cause-and-effect rules (if voltage is low at point A then the voltage at point B will be low) may be used to specify how good and bad signals propagate through the system. Given a body of test results, forward and backward deduction can be used to generate a list of components known to be good and a list of components suspected to be faulty.

Each of these models can be used by the ADS to recommend the next best test and to generate a fault hypothesis (i.e., the list of components in the system which are candidates for causing the failure). The ADS steps through the models in a predetermined order. Future versions of the ADS will reason about which model is best suited for a particular troubleshooting session.

The ADS controls the system models and data with the following core control strategy:

1. At the beginning of the session, analyze the fault signature for evidence of false alarms, multiple faults and repeated symptoms.
2. Use the cheapest model possible to reduce the fault hypothesis.
3. For each test under consideration, use the current system model to estimate the expected gain to cost ratio and select the test with the highest ratio.
4. Whenever a test is recommended, estimate the expected cost of fault isolation by testing versus the cost of fault isolation by swapping and choose the cheapest.
5. After a test is executed, use the current system model to update the fault hypothesis.

As long as a model can continue to recommend tests which reduce the fault hypothesis, the ADS will continue to use it. When a model fails (usually because it cannot recommend a test and ambiguity still exists), the ADS advances to the

next model.

Adaptation ... A third difficulty is especially pertinent to fielding intelligent maintenance aids for new systems. In these cases it is difficult to predict what will be the predominant failure modes.

The ADS utilizes current component failure rates, test execution costs, etc. to influence all of the ADS system models (except the pre-computed test tree) by biasing the test selections and test/repair tradeoff decisions. These are performed by using generic equations utilizing entropy reduction and simple expectancy theory.

A second type of adaptation uses symbolic reasoning and does not directly influence any of the device models. Here, the ADS is identifying trends that suggest that the actual device behavior is not consistent with the device models and warning messages are presented to the technician. The ADS extracts a set of anomalously identified production rules which mark certain scenarios as being "anomalous".

ADS operation ... The ADS is menu driven and offers the following options to the technician: Execute recommended test, Request test description, Request test justification, Refuse test, Choose own test (from list), Accept repair recommendation, Request display of current fault hypothesis, Request simulation of selected fault, Choose own repair, and Access notes from previous sessions.

It is important to note that the technician is always provided an estimate of how long the remaining tests should take and an estimate of how long it should take to replace all of the assemblies which are still fault candidates. Thus, the technician can stop the diagnostic session and replace the entire ambiguity group (it might be a single higher-level assembly) if turnaround time is more critical than spares cost.

IDSS STATUS

The IDSS is a Navy advanced development program to demonstrate the feasibility of the integrated diagnostic concept. The demonstration software runs on two hosts at the present time - a Sun workstation operating under Unix and a MicroVAX II minicomputer running under MicroVMS. All software is written in Ada.

The WSTA has completed government acceptance testing and is in Beta site testing prior to unrestricted release to government and industry in June 1989. As mentioned earlier, it is presently being

applied in demonstration efforts on several Navy weapon systems. The ADS is undergoing government acceptance testing prior to release to selected Beta sites for further debugging. The ADA is under development and is expected to be completed in February 1990. As mentioned earlier, the inclusion of existing DoD and commercial technical information authoring systems into the framework of TIATA is under study, and a decision will be made regarding the feasibility of this approach in time to commence work on the tool to assure completion in time for a demonstration of the overall IDSS concept in December 1990. The FA is under development with the same expected completion schedule as TIATA.

SUMMARY

The Navy's Integrated Diagnostic Support System program has heavily emphasized the development of tools to create and manage diagnostic data. This is believed to be the direction that all maintenance systems, including traditional ATE are moving toward. The fault isolation system of the 90's will be configured more like today's engineering workstation with decision making enhancements and tradeoff capabilities for the diagnostic technician. Diagnostic software like ADS will be embedded in weapon systems to conserve space and to enable real time fault isolation and performance monitoring. The system speed, and data management access, control and storage capabilities will be vastly superior to what is available today. The IDSS generic tools will interface with the new technologies and enable the maintenance technician to efficiently and confidently isolate weapon system failures. The first IDSS software tools to be completed, WSTA and ADS will greatly improve diagnostic design, testability and maintenance capability of the Navy. The completed IDSS will, for the first time, allow for the application of a systems engineering life cycle approach to the development of an effective diagnostic capability.

References

1. VHDL Language Reference Manual, IEEE Standard 1076-1987, March 1988, Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers.
2. V.D. Agrawal and M.R. Mercer, "Testability Measures -- What Do They Tell Us?", Proc. IEEE Test Conference, 1982.

3. R.A. DePaul, "Logic Modelling as a Tool for Testability", Proc. AUTOTESTCON '85, 1985, pp. 203-207.
4. W.R. Simpson, "Active Testability Analysis and Interactive Fault Isolation using STAMP", Proc. AUTOTESTCON '87, 1987, pp. 105-111.
5. K.R. Pattipati and M.G. Alexandridis, "Time-Efficient Sequencer of Tests (TEST)", Proc. AUTOTESTCON '85, 1985, pp. 49-62.
6. A.J. Magliero and R. Leong, "ADS - The IDSS Adaptive Diagnostic System", Proc. AUTOTESTCON '87, 1987, pp. 61-64.
7. R. Milne, "The Theory of Responsibilities", SIGART News, July 1985, pp. 25-29.
8. F. Pepitone, "The FIS Electronics Troubleshooting System", Computer, July 1986, pp. 68-78.